

Donald Trump: The Ghost is Back

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Abstract: American political arena is boisterous and cannibalistically dangerous where only the fittest survive. This article targets to analyzing how the former president Donald Trump survived from many allegorically deaths given to him from political one to the physical ones by focusing on his ability of resilience and his capacity to rebirth from his ashes.

Keywords: Survive, Donald Trump, allegorical, cases, Republicans, Democrats.

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Introduction

The former president makes a historical and Improbable comeback four years after being defeated by Joe Biden in 2020. This comeback is all the more improbable that he was buried by analysts and politicians who was interested in the American pollical area due to many cases and his ban from social networks. Trump had to survive from many obstacles as he says himself shortly after he had an advance over his opponent Kamala Harris by winning one of the most important Swing States Pennsylvania. "We overcome obstacles that nobody thought we could" says Trump. The aim of this article is to analyze how traditional media and internal and external bashing combined to the legal cases have failed in symbolically killing Donald Trump? c

1. Donald Trump is Dead: The Media Say

In the history of the human kind; there some people who never abdicate. Donald Trump is one among them. Right after his defeat in 2020, there was a campaign that he was victim by those who do not really like them. During his first term. Trump was not in good terms with the media. He treated them as being liars. Trump calls journalists as "threat to democracy"; "the enemy of the people", "fake", "crooked bastards". Hence the title of Columbia Journalism Review: "Trumps Wins and the Press Loses". The word used by Donald Trump shows clearly to what extent his relationships with the media spoiled one. During his first term administration, the Republic man used to give his schedules and news through his social media account the former Twitter.

Immediately after his defeat in 2020 by the Democrat Joe Biden; Trump was taken away from the social network Twitter. This ban was "the first and the only time a sitting head of state was kicked off the platform" says The FreePress. A decision that was issued just to silence him and make forgotten. The American establishment failed one again. He created his own social network

where he keeps on communicating with his people and supporters. The aim behind this decision has many and various aims. The first one is to humiliate him after the Capitol attack and raise indignation for the former president. And the second one is more ideological. Trump has many supporters with whom he communicates constantly. The White House authorities thought in cutting his link with his supporters they will soon forget about him turns out to be a big mistake as he signs a wonderful and unbelievable come back. The company states:

we view Twitters by leaders within the pollical context that defines them and enforce our rules accordingly. In banning the president in 2021, Twitter was responding in real time to what ten CEO Jack Dorsey called 'an extraordinary and untenable circumstance; forcing us to focus all our actions on public safety.' (Why Twitter Really Banned Trump, pp. 2, 3)

But the decision of preventing citizens from expressing themselves poses a problem of democracy and the freedom of expression. These should be unalienable right of any huma, being. how a former United States's President can be humiliated to such an extent. "I don't like any body censored or taken away from the right to post a message on Twitter or Facebook. I don't agree with that, I don't accept that" says the former Mexican politician Obrador.

2. The Failure of Internal and External Bashing Campaign

In the political field, the American administration does not leave a ground for him. Within the Republican party, Donald trump suffers the divisions. It was not easy at first for him to impose himself as a serious candidate who is capable of beating then candidate of the Democrats. The final fight within the Republican was whit Nikki Haley. She was a real candidate and was taken seriously as the only

capable of beating Trump in the caucuses. The international reputation of Donald Trump temperament does not help him in the western international communities. The titles of the international media show a campaign against the elected president Donald Trump. For the “pourquoi le Retour de Donald Trump n’est pas une bonne chose» (Why Donald Trump is not a Good Thing); CNN entitles: Trump Seeds Disinformation as he Sets Courses for a Possible Oval Return”; ABC News: Trump Presidency could Damage Economy if he Weakens Democracy”, CNN mentions: Trump’s Victory could Mean US Withdraw for Ukraine in War with Russia”, “JD Vance is a Bit Populist”, “De Paria à Président: la Résurrection” for France 24. They could have many other different titles, from different countries; but what they have in common is that they do not show sympathy for trump.

The lesson to learn from with all these events is that the American population is either mysterious or the western culture do not understand them. Another conclusion that can be drawn from this is that people cannot be imposed a leader. American people choose according to their need and requirement. Since the entrance of Donald Trump in the American political scene a little bit more than eight years, the polls do not come true.

3. Trump Overcomes the Legal Cases

Many observers and analysts converged that owing to the cases that former president is confronted, he cannot survive politically. So, his political death was acted. But the man is like a ghost. He has Donald Trump this capacity to resurrect himself from his ashes.

The New York Attorney General Letitia James’ civil fraud case against Trump for overstating the current market value of his properties in the personal financial statements he had submitted to lenders and insurance companies, came to trial without a jury before Judge Arthur Engoron. Normally, civil fraud requires a plaintiff to prove that a victim believed and relied on the truth of the statements, and suffered damages as a result.

But the Attorney General successfully argued that a special anti-fraud statute, New York Executive Law § 63(12), allows her to recover disgorgement of benefits received without showing that anyone relied on or was harmed by the false statements. Judge Arthur Engoron entered a judgment against Trump in February for \$354 million in disgorgement, plus interest, which would have required him to post a \$464 million bond to obtain a stay pending appeal. The appellate division allowed Trump to post a reduced bond of \$175 million to stay enforcement of the judgment pending appeal (Media Tip Sheets, Syracuse University News)

This case of fraud is not the only approach the American justice has against the former president. Shortly after, he is overwhelmed with falsifying his business records to avoid paying taxes. On May 30, 2024, the jury found Trump guilty under NYPL § 175.10 of “falsifying business records to commit fraud and to conceal another crime, although the jury did not have to indicate who was defrauded or what other crime Trump was supposed to be sentenced on September 18, but Judge Merchan granted Trump’s request to postpone sentencing until after the election. Sentencing is currently scheduled for November 26.” Says Ellen Mbuqe.

Trump is also annoyed by the Federal Election Interference Case for a while before this charge also collapses like a cartoon castle. It has been delayed by questions about presidential immunity, and now also by technical issues around special

prosecutor Jack Smith appointment. These preliminary issues will need to be resolved before the case can proceed on the merits. Under the Court’s ruling, a president has absolute immunity for anything plausibly connected to his presidential functions, including the most blatant kinds of corruption (such as selling presidential pardons to the highest bidder, or directing the military to assassinate a political rival). (Media Tip Sheets)

The second preliminary issue is whether Jack Smith’s appointment as special prosecutor was constitutional, and if not whether the case should be dismissed. As discussed below, Judge Eileen Cannon dismissed the classified documents case against Trump on the grounds that Smith’s appointment was unconstitutional. That decision is currently on appeal, and Chutkan stated on the record that she did not find Judge Cannon’s ruling to be “very persuasive.” Judge Chutkan will likely decide that special prosecutor Jack Smith can proceed with the prosecution, but the process may be delayed further for briefing on that issue, and the ultimate ruling on Judge Cannon’s dismissal could derail the election interference case.

After months of slow walking the case, on July 15, 2024, Judge Cannon dismissed the government’s indictment, determining that the Justice Department regulation under which Special Prosecutor Jack Smith was appointed was unconstitutional under the appointments clause of the Constitution.

Now what about if Trump wins the election? There is little doubt that he will cause the federal election interference and classified documents cases to be dismissed, either by appointing loyalists to take over the prosecution in the Justice Department, or by issuing himself a presidential pardon. The Supreme Court has signaled in its immunity decision that a self-pardon is within the President’s absolute authority.

However, a presidential pardon only applies to federal crimes, so it would not prevent any of the state prosecutions or cases from continuing. It is not clear whether a state prison sentence could be implemented against a sitting president, or how it could be implemented, or whether some sort of federal supremacy would prevent the states from interfering with the activities of an elected president.

Conclusion

It clearly comes out of this analysis that the American people are mysterious. They decided to give their destiny to a man who is convicted and who has many cases in instruction. However, it is insignificant if we consider how resilient is Donald Trump, him who allegorically survived from many assassinations either physically or politically. Let’s hope that his personal capacity of resilience will be beneficial for the United States of America for the next four years.

Webography

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